

ZOOLOGY

FURTHER SURVIVAL OF WHITE STORKS *CICONIA CICONIA* L. UNDER ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION OF ARARAT PLAIN OF ARMENIA

**Aghababyan K.,
Khanamirian G.,
Khechoyan A.,
Khachatryan A.,
Manjikyan A.,**

*BirdLinks Armenia NGO (former TSE Towards Sustainable Ecosystems) NGO
Yerevan, Armenia*

Pahutyan N.,

*BirdLinks Armenia NGO (former TSE Towards Sustainable Ecosystems) NGO
The Scientific Technological Center of Organic and Pharmaceutical Chemistry NAS RA
Yerevan, Armenia*

Martirosyan B.,

Babayan N.,

*BirdLinks Armenia NGO (former TSE Towards Sustainable Ecosystems) NGO
Yerevan, Armenia*

Melkumyan E.,

*Public Relations Division, RA Ministry of Environment
Yerevan, Armenia*

Sayadyan A.

*Hazardous Substances and Waste Policy Department, RA Ministry of Environment
Yerevan, Armenia*

Abstract

Monitoring of the White Storks *Ciconia ciconia* in Ararat Plain of Armenia was continued in 2022–2023 after the implementation of the mitigation measures against the novelty threat, which was discovered in 2019–2021. The storks were becoming contaminated with the undetermined agent of plant oil and/or fish fat nature, which was impeding their flying abilities. The average percentage of contaminated storks (monitored in 35 villages) grew from 5% in 2019 to 21% in 2020 and then to 58% in 2021. The joint strategy developed and implemented by the state and non-governmental organizations was aimed at the improvement of waste management of over 300 producers of fish, chips, and canned food. As a result, the average percentage of the contaminated nestlings declined from 55% in 2021 to 34% in 2022 ($t = -4.36$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.00$), and then to 22% in 2023 ($t = -2.52$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.0164$). The number of strongly polluted nestlings, which were in critical condition, showed some decline but not at a significant level. Further short-term and long-term measures are recommended.

Keywords: White Stork, *Ciconia ciconia*, Contamination, Wetland, Armenia.

Introduction

In Armenia the wetlands are of high conservation importance, hosting a high number of breeding and migratory waterbirds of global and national conservation concern, such as White-headed Duck *Oxyura leucocephala*, Ferruginous Pochard *Aythya nyroca*, Common Pochard *Aythya ferina*, Northern Lapwing *Vanellus vanellus*, and White-tailed Lapwing *Vanellus leucurus*. Despite that, the wetlands of Ararat Plain have declined during the last 70 years from 31,000 ha down to about 20,000 ha (Aghababyan 2011). Also, the wetlands of Ararat Plain are potentially susceptible to pollution, being located in the region of intensive agriculture and high-level urbanization (Aghababyan 2011; Aghababyan *et al.* 2013; 2020). Following European experience of using the White Storks *Ciconia ciconia* L. (hereafter storks) as an indicator of wetland ecosystems (Hornberger 1967; Ilichev 1990; Hötter & Thomsen 2013), we developed similar citizen science around storks in Armenia – a long-term effort that has been initiated in 2005 and continues until now (Aghababyan 2011; Aghababyan *et al.* 2020). Among other things,

the effort is dedicated to (1) the identification of the stork population size and dynamics, (2) the measurement of trends in stork breeding success in Armenia, (3) justification of the conservation status of the species in Armenia and development of conservation measures, if necessary.

The recently emerged environmental pollution became detrimental to the populations of the storks of the Ararat Plain of Armenia. The storks were becoming contaminated with the undetermined agent of plant oil and/or fish fat nature, which was impeding their flying abilities, and increasing their mortality (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022). The issue emerged in 2019, while the joint strategy for mitigating the issue was developed at the end of 2021, during a series of seminars implemented between the Ministry of Environment, Environmental Protection and Mining Inspection Body (hereinafter Environmental Inspection), and CSOs. The strategy was aimed at enforcing all producers (which can possibly have fat or oil-containing waste) to deal with the waste according to the prescribed protocols.

This paper summarizes the results of the continued monitoring of the situation with the storks and the pollution during 2022-2023, trying to identify – whether the joint strategy had a positive effect on the storks and the wetland ecosystems.

Study Area

The study area is located in the Ararat Plain of Armenia (Figure 1) and is represented by a combination of settlements, orchards, vineyards, gardens, wetlands, semideserts, and abandoned salinized arable lands.

Figure 1. Study area.

Methods

We conducted an annual monitoring program of the storks starting in 2006 covering the Ararat, Armarvir, Aragatsotn, Yerevan, Lori, Shirak, and Vayots Dzor provinces. Additional studies of the contaminated storks were conducted in 2019-2023 and covered only the Ararat Plain. Data collection involved 18 expeditions lasting a total of 21 days and covering 42 locations. Results of the survey of 2019-2021 were already published (Aghababayan *et al.* 2022) and now are supplemented with some additional data, which are repeated here for comparison with the data of 2022-2023.

Monitoring included counts of breeding pairs and nest success from 485 stork nests. The data were collected via direct observations by our team and with the assistance of villagers who served as citizen scientists. The nests were labeled with individual numbers, and villagers provided quick feedback on every unusual occasion—e.g., construction of new nests in the village,

storks' injury cases, and, starting from 2019 forward, storks with contaminated plumage.

At each nest, we also recorded the number of contaminated storks, categorized into three levels based on how much smearing each had. Storks were “slightly contaminated” when the lower part of the neck and belly was smeared, having a pale greyish-buff color, “medium contaminated” when the neck, belly, and part of wings were smeared, having a dark greyish-buff, and “strongly contaminated,” when smearing covered almost the entire stork.

Villagers were provided with wall calendars to collect data on stork nests. In addition, to try to understand the possible source of pollution, we conducted open-ended interviews with villagers.

The collected data were stored in a Microsoft Access 2003 database (later transferred into Microsoft Office 2010) for further data analysis. Statistical analyses were carried out with Excel 2010 (MS Office 2010) and

R program package. The analyses include the measurement of central tendencies and the calculation of statistically significant differences between variables. The paired samples t-test and/or Wilcoxon test were used to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the average differences between observations for different years are significantly different from zero (Daniel & Cross 2013). Mapping was conducted with QGIS Desktop 3.30.2.

In parallel to the research works, the rescue works have been implemented, and although they do not have a direct relation to the conducted study, they have decreased the mortality of the storks.

Results

Distribution and scale of the storks' pollution before the intervention, in 2019-2021, most of which was published in Aghababayan et al. (2022)

In 2019, contaminated storks were found in five villages, mainly in Hovtashen village, in 42 nests (Table 1, Figure 2a). The total number of contaminated

storks included 125 nestlings and 84 adult storks, with most being contaminated at a medium level, and several at strong levels.

In the 35 villages observed, on average, 5% ($\pm 0.03\%$ SE) of the nestlings were contaminated.

In 2020 contaminated storks were found in 15 villages, in 95 nests (Table 2, Figure 2b). The total number of contaminated nestlings was 285, and the number of contaminated adult storks was 192, with all the adults showing some smearing.

On average, 20% ($\pm 4\%$ SE) of the nestlings were contaminated in the monitored villages.

In 2021, contaminated storks were found in 28 villages, in 178 nests (Table 3, Figure 2c). The total number of contaminated nestlings was 534, along with 356 contaminated adults, all of whom were slightly contaminated.

On average, 55% ($\pm 6\%$) of the nestlings were contaminated.

Table 1.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2019.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
2	Azatashen	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
3	Khachpar	18	52	2	0	0	54	2	4%
4	Hayanist	9	24	3	0	0	27	3	11%
5	Howtashat	25	77	0	0	0	77	0	0%
6	Nizami	6	18	2	0	0	20	2	10%
7	Zorak	5	15	0	0	0	15	0	0%
8	Dashtavan	18	51	0	0	0	51	0	0%
9	Darakert	11	34	0	0	0	34	0	0%
10	Norabats	2	4	0	0	0	4	0	0%
11	Darbnik	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
12	Ghukasavan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	36	0	21	71	22	114	114	100%
14	Noramarg	4	8	4	0	0	12	4	33%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	118	0	0	0	118	0	0%
16	Yeghegnut	40	115	0	0	0	115	0	0%
17	Jrarat	8	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
18	Metsamor	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
19	Haykashen	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
20	Gay	8	26	0	0	0	26	0	0%
21	Lusagyugh	4	13	0	0	0	13	0	0%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	8	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
24	Aratashen	3	8	0	0	0	8	0	0%
25	Khoronk	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
26	Artimet	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
27	Haytagh	2	8	0	0	0	8	0	0%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	14	0	0	0	14	0	0%
30	Sipanik	10	28	0	0	0	28	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	48	0	0	0	48	0	0%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	37	0	0	0	37	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	19	0	0	0	19	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	74	0	0	0	74	0	0%
35	Armash	22	67	0	0	0	67	0	0%
	Totals	368	981	32	71	22	1106	125	

Table 2.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2020.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
2	Azatashen	2	5	0	0	0	5	0	0%
3	Khachpar	18	32	22	0	0	54	22	41%
4	Hayanist	9	20	11	0	0	31	11	35%
5	Howtashat	25	45	35	0	0	80	35	44%
6	Nizami	6	5	6	5	3	19	14	74%
7	Zorak	5	8	6	2	0	16	8	50%
8	Dashtavan	18	18	29	7	2	56	38	68%
9	Darakert	11	11	16	7	2	36	25	69%
10	Norabats	2	3	3	0	0	6	3	50%
11	Darbnik	4	9	5	0	0	14	5	36%
12	Ghukasavan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	35	59	40	5	7	111	52	47%
14	Noramarg	4	5	4	3	0	12	7	58%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	78	46	3	0	127	49	39%
16	Yeghegnut	40	121	0	0	0	121	0	0%
17	Jrarat	8	13	11	0	0	24	11	46%
18	Metsamor	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
19	Haykashen	4	11	0	0	0	11	0	0%
20	Gay	8	23	0	0	0	23	0	0%
21	Lusagyugh	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	8	25	0	0	0	25	0	0%
24	Aratashen	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
25	Khoronk	2	4	2	0	0	6	2	33%
26	Artimet	3	10	0	0	0	10	0	0%
27	Haytagh	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	14	0	0	0	14	0	0%
30	Sipanik	10	29	0	0	0	29	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	47	0	0	0	47	0	0%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	34	0	0	0	34	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	73	0	0	0	73	0	0%
35	Armash	22	68	0	0	0	68	0	0%
	Totals	367	853	239	32	14	1138	285	

Table 3

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2021.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated Storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	3	0	2	0	5	2	40%
2	Azataashen	2	0	6	0	0	6	6	100%
3	Khachpar	18	6	12	17	21	56	50	89%
4	Hayanist	9	9	7	2	11	29	20	69%
5	Howtashat	25	23	28	25	0	76	53	70%
6	Nizami	6	0	8	6	4	18	18	100%
7	Zorak	5	0	2	4	9	15	15	100%
8	Dashtavan	18	0	9	19	26	54	54	100%
9	Darakert	11	0	12	8	13	33	33	100%
10	Norabats	2	0	4	2	0	6	6	100%
11	Darbnik	4	0	6	3	4	13	13	100%
12	Ghukasavan	2	2	4	0	0	6	4	67%
13	Hovtashen	36	32	39	21	16	108	76	70%
14	Noramarg	4	4	4	2	0	10	6	60%
15	Yeraskhahun	41	59	24	26	14	123	64	52%
16	Yeghegnut	40	118	0	0	0	118	0	0%
17	Jrarat	8	0	16	5	2	23	23	100%
18	Metsamor	2	4	3	0	0	7	3	43%
19	Haykashen	4	10	2	0	0	12	2	17%
20	Gay	8	15	7	3	0	25	10	40%
21	Lusagyugh	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
22	Aknashen	3	7	2	1	0	10	3	30%
23	Griboyedov	8	18	5	0	0	27	5	22%
24	Aratashen	3	2	2	5	0	9	7	78%
25	Khoronk	2	4	3	0	0	7	3	43%
26	Artimet	3	2	5	2	0	9	7	78%
27	Haytagh	2	0	2	4	2	8	8	100%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	5	0	6	4	15	10	67%
30	Sipanik	10	31	0	0	0	31	0	0%
31	Araksavan	16	19	18	12	0	49	30	61%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	35	0	0	0	35	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	20	0	0	0	20	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	75	0	0	0	75	0	0%
35	Armash	22	69	0	0	0	69	0	0%
	Totals	368	587	233	175	126	1125	534	

Concluding the intermediary results we can state that, the average percent of the polluted nestlings in 35 observed villages grew from 5% in 2019 to 20% in 2020 ($t = 3.585$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.001$), and then to 55% in 2021 ($t = 6.903$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$) (Figure 3). The number of strongly polluted nestlings (out of the total number of polluted nestlings), that were in critical condition, didn't change significantly from 2019 to 2020 ($t = 1.18$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.2448$), although their percentage from the total number of polluted nestlings, declined from 18% in 2019 to 5% in 2020. The number and percentage of strongly polluted nestlings again increased to 24% in 2021 ($t = 3.42$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.002$).

Distribution and scale of the storks' pollution after the intervention, in 2022-2023

In 2022 contaminated storks were found in 29 villages, in 128 nests (Table 4, Figure 2d). The total number of contaminated nestlings was 383, along with 223 slightly contaminated adults. On average, 34% ($\pm 4\%$ SE) of the nestlings were contaminated.

In 2023 contaminated storks were found in 26 villages, in 145 nests (Table 5, Figure 2e). The total number of contaminated nestlings was 435, along with 208 slightly contaminated adults. On average, 22 ($\pm 3\%$ SE) of the nestlings were contaminated.

Table 4.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2022.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	2	4	0	2	0	6	2	33%
2	Azatashen	2	3	4	0	0	7	4	57%
3	Khachpar	18	28	10	14	8	60	32	53%
4	Hayanist	12	31	0	3	0	34	3	9%
5	Howtashat	25	52	7	10	4	73	21	29%
6	Nizami	15	18	20	4	0	42	24	57%
7	Zorak	11	34	0	6	0	40	6	15%
8	Dashtavan	23	68	6	8	0	82	14	17%
9	Darakert	11	7	10	9	4	30	23	77%
10	Norabats	2	2	2	3	0	7	5	71%
11	Darbnik	6	22	0	0	0	22	0	0%
12	Ghukasavan	2	3	2	0	0	5	2	40%
13	Hovtashen	36	44	28	24	8	104	60	58%
14	Noramarg	4	5	3	2	0	10	5	50%
15	Yeraskhahun	60	154	0	22	18	194	40	21%
16	Yeghegnut	40	72	0	30	12	114	42	37%
17	Jrarat	8	4	10	4	5	23	19	83%
18	Metsamor	2	5	3	0	0	8	3	38%
19	Haykashen	4	8	3	0	0	11	3	27%
20	Gay	8	17	0	4	2	23	6	26%
21	Lusagyugh	4	9	1	0	0	10	1	10%
22	Aknashen	3	8	2	0	0	10	2	20%
23	Griboyedov	16	48	4	8	0	60	12	20%
24	Aratashen	3	3	2	4	0	9	6	67%
25	Khoronk	2	3	3	0	0	6	3	50%
26	Artimet	3	4	4	2	0	10	6	60%
27	Haytagh	2	2	2	2	2	8	6	75%
28	Mkhchyan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	7	2	4	2	15	8	53%
30	Sipanik	10	28	0	4	0	32	4	13%
31	Araksavan	16	29	12	9	0	50	21	42%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	33	0	0	0	33	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	18	0	0	0	18	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	73	0	0	0	73	0	0%
35	Armash	22	66	0	0	0	66	0	0%
	Totals	420	918	140	178	65	1301	383	

Table 5.

Distribution of contaminated white storks among 35 surveyed villages in 2023.

#	Village	Number of nests	Conditional level of contamination of white storks in the nests				Number of nestlings	Number and % of contaminated storks	
			Clean	Slightly	Medium	Strong			
1	Geghanist	9	14	0	1	0	15	1	7%
2	Azatashen	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
3	Khachpar	12	28	2	4	0	34	6	18%
4	Hayanist	16	8	10	12	11	41	33	80%
5	Howtashat	25	58	10	8	0	76	18	24%
6	Nizami	24	37	5	11	9	62	25	40%
7	Zorak	12	18	0	6	9	33	15	45%
8	Dashtavan	36	33	5	37	17	92	59	64%
9	Darakert	9	16	8	2	0	26	10	38%
10	Norabats	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
11	Darbnik	13	22	1	2	9	34	12	35%
12	Ghukasavan	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0%
13	Hovtashen	28	49	26	4	2	81	32	40%
14	Noramarg	4	9	2	0	0	11	2	18%
15	Yeraskhahun	39	65	9	10	1	85	20	24%
16	Yeghegnut	36	77	18	5	4	104	27	26%
17	Jrarat	8	15	4	2	0	21	6	29%
18	Metsamor	2	5	2	0	0	7	2	29%
19	Haykashen	4	8	2	0	0	10	2	20%
20	Gay	8	19	3	2	0	24	5	21%
21	Lusagyugh	15	37	2	0	0	39	2	5%
22	Aknashen	3	9	0	0	0	9	0	0%
23	Griboyedov	31	47	14	15	1	27	30	39%
24	Aratashen	10	21	0	5	1	27	6	22%
25	Khoronk	17	47	0	0	0	47	0	0%
26	Artimet	21	251	52	42	7	352	101	29%
27	Haytagh	2	5	2	0	0	7	2	29%
28	Mkhchyan	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0%
29	Dimitrov	4	10	2	2	0	14	4	29%
30	Sipanik	9	20	5	0	0	25	5	20%
31	Araksavan	15	28	8	0	0	36	8	22%
32	Pokr Vedi	12	36	0	0	0	36	0	0%
33	Lusarat	6	18	0	0	0	18	0	0%
34	Surenavan	24	71	0	0	0	71	0	0%
35	Armash	23	67	2	0	0	69	2	3%
	Totals	485	1175	194	170	71	1560	435	

Figure 2. Pattern of white storks' contamination in 2019-2023.

Thus, the average percent of the polluted nestlings in 35 observed villages declined from 55% in 2021 to 34% in 2022 ($t = -4.36$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.001$), and then to 22% in 2023 ($t = -2.52$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.0164$) (Figure 3). The number of strongly polluted nestlings, which

were in critical condition, showed some decline from 24% in 2021 to 17% in 2022, which is not statistically significant though ($t = -1.24$, d.f. = 34, $p = 0.2226$), and then didn't change significantly in 2023 making 16% ($t = 0.14$, d.f. = 34, $p < 0.8827$).

Figure 3. Change of the percent of polluted nestlings in 35 observed villages in 2019-2023.

White storks' mortality and rescue

In 2022, over 40 storks died, but 132 were rescued, cleaned, and released. In 2023, none of the dead storks were recorded, though 26 were rescued. Most of the birds that died in 2022 were fledglings that had been severely contaminated at their nests. The smearing disallowed them from flying, and nestlings that attempted their first flight dropped from the nests, breaking their legs and wings.

Discussion

The storks' contamination declined statistically significantly and consistently from 2022 to 2023. However, the number of strongly contaminated storks declined somewhat in 2022 (although not significantly) and then remained almost the same in 2023.

The possible explanation of the observed decline of contaminated storks can be related to the strategy, jointly developed and implemented by the Ministry of Environment, Environmental Inspection, BirdLinks Armenia NGO, and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO. One of the conclusions made in the previous period (2019-2021) was that several short-term measures should be implemented urgently (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022). Those include (1) inventory by the Environmental Inspection of all the producers of fish, canned food, chips, etc., which can possibly have a fat or oil-containing waste; (2) enforcing all producers to provide annual reports on their waste, according to the legislation; (3) development of the annual cycle of comparison of the volume of the waste recorded in the annual report with the production volume to find possible violations (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022). The Environmental Inspection identified over 300 such producers within the region of contaminated storks and implemented the planned inspections during 2022-2023, meanwhile broadcasting these steps among producers through its own Public Relations unit and with the help of the NGOs. At the same time, the Hazardous Substances and Waste Policy Department and Public Rela-

tions Division of the Ministry of Environment developed and distributed educational materials to popularize the waste-related issues, obligations, and solutions for fish farmers and producers. Therefore, the observed decline of the storks' contamination can be related to the improvement of waste-related behavior of the fish farmers and producers of chips and canned food.

The fact that the average number of strongly contaminated storks didn't decline significantly, most probably means that there are several spots where contamination still remains very intensive. Specifically, there are several villages, where the number of strongly contaminated storks is still enormously high: Darbnik – 9 strongly contaminated out of 12 contaminated (75%), Zorak – 9/15 (60%), Nizami – 9/25 (36%), Hayanist – 11/33 (33%), and Dashtavan – 17/59 (29%). Extraction of these five villages from the sample of 2023 decreases the average percentage of strongly contaminated storks down to 4%. These five villages are located within a single circle and thus, it is essential now to intensify the inspection and education efforts on this circle.

The agents smearing the storks have not yet been identified. However, the fact that the storks' contamination declined after the beginning of the inspections indirectly proves the hypothesis (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022) that the contamination comes from the fish producers (internal organs of the fish full of fish fat, which are thrown after the fish gutting) and chips and/or canned oil producers (wasted plant oil improperly disposed of).

As concluded in previous research (Aghababyan *et al.* 2022), the country's existing legislation is sufficient for food producers to have an annual report on waste, which must describe the volume of the waste and the method and terms of its disposal. However, a tracking system and enforcement of the regulation were needed.

With that consideration, in 2022 the Ministry of Environment issued a new decree N 262-L on approval

of the Fish-farms' Waste Management Guide. The decree was broadcast through the regular channels by the Public Relations Division of the Ministry, but also through the educational brochure "Fish-farms' Waste Management Guide" developed by the Hazardous Substances and Waste Policy Department of the Ministry and distributed through the series of seminars with the fish-farmers and canned food producers, as well as through the Association of Fish-farmers of Armenia.

The Environmental Inspection examined all the producers of fish, chips, and canned food, forcing them to provide annual reports on the waste. BirdLinks Armenia NGO and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO broadcasted the issue and the law enforcement through TV interviews and social media.

Considering the described issues, the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Territorial Administration and Infrastructure have made legislative changes, proposing those for the relevant legal acts. Specifically, in the Law "On Waste Removal and Sanitation", the regulations related to the management of biodegradable waste have been defined. Also, for the placement of other biological waste, the RA Code on Administrative Offenses (which will come into force on January 1, 2025) has established appropriate measures of responsibility for dumping waste outside of designated places and in unauthorized ways.

The joint efforts of the Ministry of Environment, Environmental Inspection, BirdLinks Armenia NGO, and Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species NGO, directed at enforcing legislation, can be considered successful, taking the decline of storks' contamination, as an indirect indication. It is necessary, therefore, to continue the consistent inspections of these producers and monitoring of the storks' populations, in order to track the efficiency of the efforts for biodiversity and ecosystems.

Conclusion

It appears that the joint strategy that was developed and implemented by the state organizations and CSOs was the right one and it already started giving positive feedback, as evidenced by the decline in the number of contaminated storks. At the moment, it is very important to continue consistent inspections of the producers of fish, chips, and canned food, and to transfer those inspections into the regular annual procedure.

Also, it is important to begin working on increasing punishments for violations of waste disposal rules, as this will motivate the producers further.

In addition, it is very important to begin the development of recycling the remains of gutted fish and used plant oil, which has significant business potential.

Eventually, it is important to protect the storks, not through the Red Data Book, but through its consideration as one of the national symbols of Armenia, and thus through increasing punishments for harming the white storks and their wetland habitats.

Acknowledgments

We are incredibly thankful to the Whitley Fund for Nature, which supported the project with the Whitley Award donated by The Friends of Whitley and further – with Continuation Funding. We are greatly thankful

to the Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Armenia for administrative support. We are very thankful to Caucasus Nature Fund and the private donors for their financial support of the storks' study and cleaning, as well as to Protection of Endemic and Endangered Species Foundation for organizing the rescue of the storks, and ZooFauna Art LLC, Mankus Ecopark LLC, Jambo Exotic Park, and Municipality of Hovtashen village for their support in the rescue of the birds. At the same time, we thank Dr. Anahit Aleksandryan for her valuable comments on the modern situation with the legislation, the Armenian State Hydrometeorological and Monitoring Service for their comments on the temperature parameters in Ararat province, and the National Statistical Service for their comments on the dynamics of canned food production. Also, we thank Manuk Manukyan, Hrach Ghazaryan, Knarik Hambarzumyan, Margarita Sharimanyan, Karine Avetisyan, Astghik Tsaturyan, and Armen Arabyan for their help in data collection, as well as Viktorya Gevorgyan for her help in statistical analysis and Asya Ghazaryan for the help in GIS analysis. Also, we are incredibly thankful to over 60 volunteers who helped us with the rescue of the storks and over 1,000 residential families in the villages of Ararat, Armavir, Lori, Shirak, and Vayots Dzor provinces for their consistent efforts in monitoring white storks in Armenia.

References

1. Adamian, M.S., Klem D. Jr. 1999. *Handbook of the Birds of Armenia*. American University of Armenia, Oakland, California: 1–649.
2. Aghababyan K. 2011. White Storks (*Ciconia ciconia* L.): Population tendencies in Armenia. *Proceedings of the International Conference "Biological Diversity and Conservation Problems of the Fauna of the Caucasus," September 26–29, Yerevan, Asoghik: 9–13.*
3. Aghababyan K., Kochinyan M., and Stepanyan L. 2013. White Storks (*Ciconia ciconia* L.) in Armenia: population, trend, and relationships to humans. In: Hötter, H. & K.-M. Thomsen (eds). *White Stork on the top? - Results of the VIth International White Stork Census 2004/05*. NABU (Naturschutzbund Deutschland e.V.), Berlin.
4. Aghababyan K. and Khanamirian G. 2014. Opportunities and restrictions for sustainable development of aquaculture in Armenia. *Рыбоводство и рыбное хозяйство [Fish farming and fisheries]* 6: 41–49, 7: 38–42.
5. Aghababyan K., Khanamirian G., Ter-Voskanyan H., Khachatryan A., Gevorgyan V. 2020. White Storks (*Ciconia ciconia* L.) in Armenia: over ten years of research for conservation. *Bird Census News* 32(1–2): 3–10.
6. Aghababyan, K., Khanamirian. G., Manukyan, M., Ghazaryan, H., Pahutyanyan N., Khechoyan. A., Hambarzumyan, K., Sharimanyan. M., Avetisyan, K., Tsaturyan. A., Arabyan, A., Sahakyan, K., Sayadyan, A., Khachatryan, A., Martirosyan, B., Gevorgyan, V., Ghazaryan, A., Sundar, G. 2022. White Storks (*Ciconia ciconia* L.) became victims of environmental pollution of Ararat Plain of Armenia. *Journal of Ecology and*

Natural Resources 6(1): 1-10. 10.23880/jenr-16000269.

7. Aghasyan A., and Kalashyan M. (eds). 2010. *Red Book of Animals of the Republic of Armenia*. Ministry of Nature Protection, Yerevan. Asoghik.

8. Daniel, W.W. & Cross, C.L. 2013. *Biostatistics. A Foundation for Analysis in the Health Sciences*. JohnWiley & Sons, Inc. Hoboken, NJ, USA.

9. Hornberger, F. 1967. *Der Weiss-Storch. [The White Stork.]* Wittenberg. Lutherstadt.

10. Hötter, H. & K.-M. Thomsen (eds.). 2013. *White Stork on the top? - Results of the VIth International White Stork Census 2004/05*. Naturschutzbund Deutschland e. V. (NABU) [Nature and Biodiversity Conservation Union], Berlin.

11. Ilichev, V.D. 1990. The White Stork as a model-problem species in optimization of relationship of human and birds. In: *Storks: distribution, ecology, protection*. Navuka I tekhnika. [Science and technology.] Minsk.